

Results of the baseline study on the prevalence of *Salmonella* spp. in holdings of breeding pigs presented

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Salmonella are bacteria that often lead to gastroenteritis in humans. A major portion of these infections is caused by the consumption of foods that are contaminated with *Salmonella*. Next to eggs and poultry, pork is among the most common sources of such infections.

In order to assess the prevalence of *Salmonella* in holdings of breeding pigs, the European Commission proposed a baseline survey in all Member States. The survey was carried out from 1 January to 31 December 2008 according to a study design prescribed by the EU. It covered at least 80% of breeding pigs in each Member State. The individual studies were preferably carried out at holdings with at least 50 breeding pigs. Representative holdings were selected in each Member State.

Germany has now presented the results of its baseline survey on the prevalence of *Salmonella* in breeding pig stocks. The regional authorities (Länder) were responsible for taking samples at the holdings, testing for *Salmonella* and collecting the data. The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) coordinated the survey, supervised the laboratory work, typed the isolates and prepared the reports.

In 45 of the 201 holdings examined, at least one out of 10 composite faecal samples taken contained *Salmonella*. In most positive holdings only one (15 holdings) or two (11 holdings) of the 10 samples examined came up positive. 58% of *Salmonella* that were found were of the most common serovars found in pigs namely *Salmonella* Derby (38%) and *Salmonella* Typhimurium (20%). These serovars were also the most common serovars found in a survey on slaughter pigs in 2006/2007.

The full version of the BfR Information in German is available on http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/208/grundlagenstudie_zum_vorkommen_von_salmonella_spp_in_zuchtschweinebestaenden_vorgelegt.pdf